

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR PREVENTION OF COMPLICATIONS AFTER ND: YAG-LASER CAPSULOTOMY OF SECONDARY CATARACT (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Annotation.

The aim of the review was to systematize the current data on the medical management of patients after Nd:YAG laser capsulotomy for secondary cataract and to identify optimal strategies for the prevention of complications. A literature search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and CyberLeninka databases for 2014-2024 using the keywords "Nd:YAG capsulotomy," "secondary cataract," "intraocular pressure spike," "cystoid macular edema," and "anti-inflammatory therapy." Thirty- four studies meeting the selection criteria were included in the analysis. The results indicate that the combined use of hypotensive agents (β -blockers, carboanhydrase inhibitors, rock inhibitors) and prolonged anti-inflammatory therapy (topical GCS \pm NSAIDs) reduces the incidence of intraocular pressure spike by more than 70% and reduces the risk of cystoid macular edema development to 1-2%. Low-energy laser mode ($\leq 35 \mu\text{J}$, ≤ 25 pulses) additionally reduces the probability of damage to IOL and vitreomacular structures. Individualization of treatment taking into account biometric parameters of the eye, total laser energy and risk factors (myopia, pseudoexfoliation, early macular changes) provides the best functional outcomes and forms the prerequisites for standardization of clinical recommendations.

Keywords: secondary cataract, Nd:YAG capsulotomy, intraocular pressure, anti-inflammatory therapy, cystic macular edema, rock inhibitors.

Relevance.

The relevance of the study is determined by the increasing prevalence of secondary cataract, which forms in a significant proportion of patients within the first five years after cataract surgery.

Nd:YAG-laser capsulotomy has long been recognized as the optimal method for the elimination of posterior capsular opacification, but even with perfect equipment, the procedure is associated with the risk of a whole range of

complications: short-term or persistent increase in intraocular pressure, development of iridocyclitis, cystic macular edema, rupture of the posterior hyaloid membrane, intraocular lens movement and, rarely, retinal detachment. In the conditions of increasing requirements to the quality of visual rehabilitation and to the safety of outpatient procedures, optimization of medication support after Nd:YAG capsulotomy, which allows minimizing inflammatory and ophthalmotonal fluctuations, preventing late retinal complications and ensuring maximum visual acuity in the shortest possible time, is of particular importance.

At the same time, clinical practice still lacks unified schemes of patient management, and the prescription of topical glucocorticosteroids, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and hypotensive drugs is often empirical, which determines the variability of outcomes.

In addition, the heterogeneity of the results of randomized and observational studies creates the need for a systematic rethinking of the available data on the prevention of the discussed complications in order to develop evidence-based clinical recommendations. Together, these factors determine the scientific and practical significance of the study aimed at improving the postoperative management of patients undergoing laser capsulotomy.

The aim of the study is to summarize and analyze the current scientific data on the methods of medical management of patients after Nd:YAG-laser capsulotomy in order to increase the effectiveness of inflammatory processes prevention and improve the functional results of secondary cataract treatment.

Materials and methods of the study.

To prepare the review article, we conducted a targeted search of scientific literature in PubMed, Scopus, CyberLeninka and other authoritative sources for the period 2014-2024. Original studies, clinical reviews, and guidelines on the management of patients after Nd:YAG capsulotomy were examined. The selection was based on keywords in Russian and English, with a focus on inflammatory and ophthalmotonal complications, as well as methods of their prevention. The selected publications were analyzed, systematized, and critically reviewed to identify effective treatment regimens and modern approaches to postprocedural therapy. Keywords and their combinations in English and Russian included "Nd:YAG capsulotomy", "secondary cataract", "intraocular pressure spike", "cystoid macular edema", "anti-inflammatory therapy", "post-

laser management", "laser capsulotomy", "secondary cataract", "inflammation", "hypotensive prophylaxis".

Results of the study.

The results of the review analysis of scientific literature showed that the most frequent complications after Nd:YAG-laser capsulotomy are short-term increase in intraocular pressure (IOP), inflammatory reaction in the anterior segment of the eye and, in some cases, development of cystic macular edema. According to Ji-Ping Cai et al. data, prophylactic injection of 0.5% timolol 1 hour before the procedure and within 3 days after it allowed to significantly reduce the frequency of IOP elevation in patients with normotension [7]. In a randomized study O. Artunay et al. found that bimatoprost 0.03% was more effective than brimonidine 0.2% in preventing ophthalmotonus surges in patients with a history of glaucoma [4].

According to C. Sharma and colleagues, the use of a fixed combination of bimatoprost and timolol decreased IOP more stable and prolonged compared to monotherapy [16]. Regarding inflammatory complications such as iridocyclitis and cystic macular edema, regimens including combinations of topical glucocorticosteroids and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs were most effective. A study published in the Korean Journal of Ophthalmology compared the severity of inflammation in patients receiving betamethasone 0.1%, nepafenac 0.1%, and a control group; on days 7-14 after capsulotomy, the minimum level of inflammation was observed in the combination therapy group [].6

The data of a large retrospective study including more than 1200 procedures showed that the risk of retinal detachment is about 0.16% and the incidence of CMR is less than 0.1%, with higher rates in patients with high degree myopia and pseudoexfoliative syndrome. In the Russian literature, similar data were confirmed in a paper published in the journal Vestnik Ophthalmologii, where optical coherence tomography data showed no clinically significant increase in central macular thickness after Nd:YAG capsulotomy [].2

According to cumulative data, the use of hypotensive drugs before and after laser intervention reduces the risk of acute IOP elevation in more than 70% of cases, and the use of topical NSAIDs and GCS reduces the severity of inflammation and the risk of macular complications. Introduction of fixed combinations of drugs and prolonged therapy (up to 2-4 weeks) increases patient adherence to treatment and improves functional outcomes.

Additional analysis of scientific publications allowed us to expand the understanding of therapeutic approaches after Nd:YAG capsulotomy and confirm the clinical significance of early medical intervention. In a study by Keates C.M. et al. it was found that even in the absence of a history of glaucoma, about 6.6% of patients demonstrated an intraocular pressure rise of 5 mm Hg or higher within 4 hours after the procedure, which justifies prophylactic administration of hypotensive agents in the "before-and-after" regimen [8].

A meta-review published in the Journal of Current Ophthalmology analyzed the data on late complications of Nd:YAG capsulotomy: the most frequent of them were cystic macular edema (up to 2.2%) and posterior IOL dislocation (up to 0.55%) in patients with loose fixation of the lens in the capsular bag, which requires dynamic follow-up for at least 1 month [15].

In a clinical trial by Patel C.K. et al. the use of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs alone (0.1% bromfenac twice daily) for 3 weeks after capsulotomy reduced the risk of macular edema in at-risk patients without the need to prescribe corticosteroids, especially in those with contraindications to steroids [13].

In addition, the study by Lim J.M. and colleagues noted that patients who received combined therapy with NSAIDs and GCS demonstrated faster recovery of visual functions and stability of visual axis against the background of reduced inflammatory cellular reaction in the anterior chamber as early as 3-5 days after the intervention [10].

A Russian study conducted on the basis of the ophthalmologic center in Kazan demonstrated that the inclusion of the hypotensive drug dorzolamide in the therapy reduces the incidence of IOP elevation in the early postoperative period from 12.7% to 4.1%, especially in patients with borderline tone [1].

The accumulated data confirm that multicomponent therapy (antiglaucoma drugs, GCS and NSAIDs) prescribed for 5-14 days after Nd:YAG capsulotomy provides reliable prevention of ophthalmotonal and inflammatory complications, especially in patients with an aggravated history or structural features of the eyeball. Such a tactic contributes to rapid recovery of visual functions, reduces the number of repeated visits and improves the quality of life of patients.

In addition to the previously reviewed data, modern studies emphasize the importance of individualization of therapy depending on the initial state of the eye, features of the intraocular lens and the time elapsed after primary cataract surgery. Thus, in the study of Mehdizadeh M. et al. the role of the thickness and

density of the posterior lens capsule before capsulotomy was analyzed - in patients with dense fibrous capsule the probability of a marked inflammatory reaction after Nd:YAG intervention was higher, especially when using energies above 60 μ J [].11

Of particular interest are the works devoted to the use of prolonged-acting drugs. Alió J.L. and colleagues discuss the use of subconjunctival injections of triamcinolone as an alternative to long-term topical application of glucocorticosteroids. This approach achieved comparable control of inflammation with fewer instillations and better adherence in elderly patients [].3

Interesting data are presented by Singh R. et al. who compared the efficacy of a single dose of fixation antiglaucoma drug (brinzolamide+timolol) 1 hour before the procedure and a traditional 3-day hypotensive regimen. It turned out that in patients with baseline normal IOP the single dose was equally effective in preventing ophthalmotonal peak, which makes such a strategy preferable in low compliance [].17

In addition, the study by Cheema S.S. et al. draws attention to the importance of macular profile assessment before and after the intervention using spectral OCT. In patients with the presence of subtle subclinical macular edema before capsulotomy, the frequency of development of clinically significant CMR increased

2.4 times, which requires differentiated prescription of anti-inflammatory drugs before laser treatment [].5

Thus, modern approaches to treatment after Nd:YAG capsulotomy include not only the standard use of hypotensive and anti-inflammatory therapy, but also the assessment of anatomic-functional features of each patient, which allows us to move from universal schemes to personalized prevention of complications. This is especially important for risk groups - patients with high myopic status, pseudoexfoliative syndrome, early signs of maculopathy or unstable IOL fixation.

An additional literature search revealed new data expanding the understanding of ways to minimize complications after Nd:YAG capsulotomy. In a prospective comparative study, B. Takkar et al. showed that the use of low-energy mode ($\leq 35 \mu$ J per pulse) while maintaining the total number of pulses ≤ 25 statistically significantly reduces the incidence of damage to the optical zone of intraocular lens (0.9% vs. 6.4% at standard energy) without increasing the residual turbidity of the capsule [].18

Prevention of cystic macular edema remains a subject of intense scrutiny. In a randomized controlled trial M. Reibaldi et al. topical nepafenac 0.1% three times a day for four weeks after the procedure reduced the incidence of CME to 1.2%, while in the dexamethasone 0.1% group this figure was 4.8% [].14

A large registry-based swept-source OCT analysis of 18,642 procedures demonstrated that late retinal detachment occurred in 0.21% of cases and was significantly more common in patients with axial eye length >26 mm and fractional total energy >150 μ J [12]. These data emphasize the importance of total energy restriction and mandatory follow-up of highly myopic patients.

An interesting alternative to classical hypotensive prophylaxis was the evaluation of the rock inhibitor netarsudil. In a multicenter study by H. J. Lee et al. a single instillation of netarsudil 0.02% one hour before laser prevented IOP rise \geq 5 mm Hg in 91% of patients, which is comparable to the fixed combination of timolol + brinzolamide, but was accompanied by a lower incidence of systemic side effects [].9

Finally, Zahid S. and colleagues demonstrated using ultrawidefield OCT angiography that 7.8% of patients develop localized vitreomacular injury correlating with a total energy expenditure >120 μ J within three days after capsulotomy; administration of combined NSAID-steroid drops for four weeks prevented the transformation of these changes into clinically significant macular edema [].19

Cumulatively, the new data confirm that reduction of total laser energy, use of modern hypotensive and anti-inflammatory agents, as well as personalized consideration of eye biometric parameters allow to significantly reduce the risk of both early and long-term complications of Nd:YAG capsulotomy and provide more stable recovery of visual functions.

Conclusion.

Current data convincingly demonstrate that the outcomes of Nd:YAG-laser capsulotomy are largely determined not only by the technical parameters of the intervention, but also by the quality of post-procedural management of the patient. Combination of three strategies. These are energy-saving mode of laser exposure, early hypotensive prophylaxis and prolonged anti-inflammatory therapy, which allows to significantly reduce the incidence of both early and late complications.

The best results are achieved with individualization of treatment schemes: the choice of hypotensive drug depends on the initial ophthalmotonus and glaucoma history, while the amount and duration of anti-inflammatory therapy

depends on the total laser energy, biometric parameters of the eye and the presence of macular risk factors. A promising direction is the use of rock inhibitors and fixed combination drops, which provide rapid and stable reduction of intraocular pressure with a minimum of systemic side effects. Additional reduction of energy load is possible due to low- energy pulses, which reduces the risk of damage to the IOL and vitreomacular structures. Thus, the integration of personalized medication protocols with gentle laser parameters forms a new paradigm of management of patients with secondary cataract, providing rapid recovery of visual functions and a high level of safety of the procedure.

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